

D10.3

Report on coordination, prioritisation, and harmonisation in the Solid Earth subdomain

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Deliverable abstract

The deliverable "D10.3 Report on Coordination, Prioritization, and Harmonisation in the Solid Earth Subdomain," primarily focuses on the strategic prioritization of activities aimed at enhancing the application of FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) principles across various Earth Science disciplines in WP10. This document provides an overview of the selected activities, explaining their prioritization based on the gap analysis and need for improvement in FAIRness. The report reflects upon the efforts of the European Plate Observing System community in embedding FAIR principles from the outset and further improving its commitment through these prioritized activities. Key initiatives include the harmonisation of metadata, implementation of Persistent Identifier systems, data and metadata lifecycle management, and the development of common vocabularies across multiple Earth Science domains. The success of these activities highlights the importance of strategic planning and prioritization in enhancing FAIRness and overall data management effectiveness in the ENVRI community.

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DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471374>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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D10.3 – Report on coordination, prioritization and harmonisation in the Solid Earth subdomain

1 Introduction

The primary objective of this deliverable is to present a comprehensive report on the coordination, prioritization, and harmonisation efforts undertaken within the Solid Earth Subdomain, with a particular focus on the implementation of FAIR principles. FAIR principles aim to establish a shared knowledge base that encourages communities to adopt standardised data practices, ultimately facilitating interoperability and data sharing. However, these principles do not provide explicit guidelines or methodologies for Research Infrastructures (RIs) to develop and implement the requisite software and technologies to actualise FAIR data.

In this deliverable, we first recall the methodology employed to transition from FAIR principles to concrete technical activities (Chapter 2). Subsequently, we summarise how the methodology was implemented (Chapter 3) and finally we discuss how the actions defined in D10.2 were prioritized in order to fill the gaps identified by the FAIR assessment and planning processes (Chapter 4).

2 Summary of the Methodology

In order to prioritize tasks and actions identified in Deliverable 10.2 (Bailo et al., 2022), we have adopted a simplified methodology influenced by the system development life cycle (SDLC) process and previous work (Bailo, 2020). This methodology aims to address the integration of FAIR principles into existing research infrastructures (RIs), which is a common challenge faced by tasks 10.3 to 10.6 in Work Package 10, and actually all RI's in ENVRIFAIR in the sub-domain work packages (WP8 to WP11).

The methodology, described in D10.2, consists of two main steps:

1. **FAIRness Assessment & Gap Analysis:** The first step is to evaluate the compliance of RIs services with detailed FAIR principles and perform a gap analysis to identify critical areas requiring technical activities. While various initiatives are currently dedicated to evaluating compliance with FAIR principles (Wilkinson, 2019), we adopted a simple approach that involved discussion-based evaluations for each FAIR principle applied to a specific RI service (as shown in Table 1A and Table 1B).
2. **Technical Activities Definition:** Based on the results of the FAIRness evaluation and identified gaps, a preliminary list of technical activities required to fulfil specific FAIR principles within the domain-specific context was devised. These activities were defined following steps from design (b) to operation (e) of the SDLC.

By utilising this methodology, we were able to define the tasks and actions outlined in Deliverable 10.2, ensuring that existing RIs can be upgraded to comply with FAIR principles in an efficient and streamlined manner, and we show how these were harmonised and prioritized in the current deliverable.

3 Gap analysis and Activities roadmap for RI services

In the current section, we report on the prioritized list of activities that were defined in the previous deliverables (D10.2) based on the methodology described in section 2. Activities are grouped by Tasks from 10.3 to 10.7.

3.1 Task 10.3 - ICS-C

EPOS has been designed with the principles of FAIRness at its core, embodying a fundamentally FAIR system. Recognising that FAIRness is a continuous journey rather than a destination, this task focuses on enhancing the FAIRness of EPOS's key component, the Integrated Core Services - Central Hub (ICS-C). This task began with harmonising the understanding of FAIR principles among the ICS-C stakeholders. This shared understanding set the stage for collaborative work. Next, a gap analysis was

conducted. Since EPOS ICS-C has already set off on the journey towards FAIRness, the gap analysis serves to fine-tune the FAIR activities and guide their prioritization.

The activities of Task 10.3 are layered, each addressing a different facet of FAIRness:

1. From the perspective of data providers (TCS): The objective is to improve the visibility and usability of their data (DDSS) by providing Persistent Identifiers (PIDs).
2. From the perspective of the ICS-C itself: The task aims to enhance the FAIRness process and improve Authentication, Authorisation, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI) integration.
3. From the consumers' perspective: The task is focused on enriching the metadata catalogue, improving the findability and accessibility of data.
4. From the reusability perspective: The task plans to establish links with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the Integrated Core Services - Distributed (ICS-D), to enhance data reusability and interoperability.

Thus, the FAIR roadmap of Task 10.3 includes actions that require the engagement of a diverse group of stakeholders with relevant skills and assets.

3.1.1 Technical activity overview and implementation roadmap

The selection and prioritization of activities within Task 10.3 were guided by the following prioritized activities:

- Provision of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) to improve data visibility and findability: this activity involved assigning unique and persistent identifiers to datasets or resources, enabling easier and more reliable access, discovery, and tracking of data over time, thus enhancing their visibility and findability. Database internal identifiers have been assigned and EPOS ERIC is negotiating with the Italian National DataCite node the ability to assign DOIs.
- Enrichment of the metadata catalogue to facilitate data discoverability and usability: This activity focuses on enhancing the metadata catalogue by adding relevant and descriptive information about datasets. By enriching the metadata, it becomes easier for users to discover and understand the content of the data, leading to improved usability and efficient data exploration. This activity was carried out by refactoring CERIF to make it more fit for purpose with respect to the requirements collected.
- Enhancement of Authentication, Authorisation, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI) integration for reliable and secure data services: This activity aims to improve the integration of the Authentication, Authorisation, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI) within data services. By enhancing AAAI integration, the activity ensures reliable and secure access to data, allowing proper authentication of users, controlling their authorised actions, and maintaining accurate records of data usage. The authentication system has been consolidated and extended to interoperate with other RIs (namely EMSO and AnaEE)
- Establishment of links with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the Integrated Core Services - Distributed (ICS-D) to promote data reusability and interoperability. This task has succeeded with the integration of EPOS assets within the ENVRI Catalogue of Services, which is now included in the EOSC marketplace, and with the establishment of ICS-D prototypes (see section 3.2).

The task progressed well with the extension of the EPOS-ERIC catalogue's metadata schema towards a more complete and richer schema, and improvements in the FAIRification of the ICS-C API. A cross-institutional effort has been made to improve the attribute values for metadata elements in the catalogue to enhance FAIRness.

One key challenge encountered was harmonising vocabularies across the diverse communities within EPOS, which proved more difficult than anticipated. However, procedures for mapping and importing into a vocabulary tool have been established, and the next step is ingestion into the semantic layer of CERIF.

These efforts towards FAIRness have been supported and accepted by the participating ENVRI research infrastructures. As co-leaders of the ENVRI-FAIR WP5 Task Force, INGV and UKRI have successfully led a significant subset of the RIs in ENVRI, namely EPOS, EMSO and AnaEE, in adopting the EPOS approach and evolving to use of OIDC for authentication and OAuth2 for authorisation.

3.2 Task 10.4 - ICS-D

ICS-D is the term for the distributed ICS services. They are to be managed from the ICS-C portal environment. The idea is to support a Virtual Research Environment (VRE) to allow a researcher or other end-user to compose workflows that after collecting and contextualising assets, typically will involve analytics, simulations and visualisations.

Integration and interoperability of the visualisation and analysis web platform with the ICS-C have been conducted with special emphasis on the FAIR principles. A demonstrator of the VRE concept has been developed focusing on visualisation and analysis platforms integrated with ICS-C. The goals of this task have thus been to implement technical elements for ICS-D to achieve FAIRness maturity and EOSC compatibility.

The ICS-D implementation in this project consists of the following components:

- SWIRRL API¹ – webservice. This is a framework used for executing workflows for staging required data and for starting the specific ICS-D, in this project specifically Enlighten-web and Jupyter notebook².
- Enlighten-web³ – This is a web application for interactive visual analysis.
- Jupyter notebook – This is a web programming environment for analysis.
- Hosting facility - Deployment of the ICS-D services at BGRM.

3.2.1 Technical activity overview and implementation roadmap

Below are the technical activities and implementations identified in D10.2. For each topic, a short status update is added (please refer to D10.5 - to be submitted by end of June 2023 - for more details).

- *From D10.2:* Metadata must be defined for the Jupyter Notebook as a service and Enlighten-web visualisation service. The metadata must be described in EPOS-DCAT-AP ttl files. We must compare our requirements with existing EPOS-DCAT-AP and identify gaps. When EPOS-DCAT-AP has been updated to fill identified gaps, the defined metadata can be ingested into CERIF.

Performed work: We have defined metadata for the ICS-D services. The metadata was defined using the SHAPENESS METADATA EDITOR, and stored in a turtle file using the EPOS-DCAT-AP vocabulary. INGV deployed a testing environment which contains these metadata in the catalogue and shows the services in the EPOS ICS-C GUI.

- *From D10.2:* For SWIRRL Jupyter notebook as an instance and Enlighten-web as an instance, the protocol does not yet allow for an authentication and authorisation procedure, but OAUTH is envisaged also with delegation.

Status: There is ongoing work within the EPOS central (ICS-C) development programme on authentication. SWIRRL does not support Authentication yet, but this will be tackled in the activities planned for evolution of such a framework, as for instance those in the framework of the EPOS Sponsored Research Activities.

- *From D10.2:* Define metadata for Enlighten-web instances. These metadata describe the visualisations created using Enlighten-web. The metadata will be created when the user stores a visualisation. For the generation and instantiation of templates for the activities related to the Enlighten-web service, we foresee that many of the templates used for Jupyter Notebook instances can be re-used or adapted. Moreover, new templates can be designed aiming at achieving specific FAIR objectives for Enlighten-web instances.

Status/performed work: SWIRRL supports generation and storage of provenance data utilising the PROV-Template Catalogue (Moreau et al., 2018). We have created a template for the

¹ <https://gitlab.com/KNMI-OSS/swirrl/swirrl-api>

² <https://jupyter.org/>

³ <https://www.norceresearch.no/en/research-theme/enlighten-web>

instantiation of an Enlighten-web Service. We have furthermore configured Enlighten-web to store specifications of visualisations on JSON files on the server. This will allow SWIRRL to include these files in the provenance for visualisation sessions.

- *From D10.2:* We must implement microservices for converting data from ICS-C workspace to Enlighten-web input data. We foresee that ICS-C workspace contents will be in the form of URLs defining searches for data. We do not want to perform these searches every time the user accesses a SWIRRL Enlighten-web instance.

Performed work: To achieve improved FAIR-ness of the visualisation sessions, we needed to enable SWIRRL to stage immutable data for the visualisations, i.e. data files be created from data search URLs from the ICS-C workspace. We have implemented data staging and data transformation into workflows that can be run by SWIRRL as part of the data staging workflow.

- *From D10.2:* Licensing is also a remaining issue for most of the ICS-D components.

Status: The intention of EPOS is to make software available as open source with a suitable licence and also to license binaries in a similar way. A Policy Group is working on this in the framework of EPOS activities, currently, alongside management of a liability disclaimer and informed consent to terms and conditions of use, cookies and personal data privacy.

- *From D10.2:* We will pursue integration of the ICS-D within the EPOS Portal (ICS-C). For the FAIR principles F4, A1, A1.1 and A1.2, compliance will depend on the way ICS-D services are made available from ICS-C.

Performed work: We have followed the EPOS work on the design of the ICS-D interface in ICS-C, as this was an important input to our work. We participated in a workshop on ICS-D GUI and technical solutions. Work is currently ongoing in EPOS on implementing the required ICS-D connectors.

- *From D10.2:* The activities concerning the FAIRness of service instances are fundamental to collect an initial baseline of metadata that can be used by SWIRRL to implement new API methods offering restoring actions. These aim to reset the Notebook or an Enlighten instance to a previous state, and to reproduce the environment and the data generated with these tools by peers. This would demonstrate an actual adoption of the FAIR capabilities of the tool in real use-cases.

Performed work: A SWIRRL JupyterLab extension has been implemented with an interactive panel that allows users to control the restoring of updates and the production of snapshots. These are developed as Jupyter lab extensions installed automatically in the notebook instances managed by SWIRRL.

3.3 Task 10.5 – Seismology

Seismology is an important founding community in EPOS which is represented by large, distributed infrastructures including several Pan-European datacentres and research institutes. One such infrastructure is ORFEUS-EIDA which is participating in ENVRI-FAIR.

The gap analysis performed in the first phase of the project yielded a set of development activities. The following section reports the status of those activities and the achieved results. Readers are referred to D10.5 (to be submitted by end of June 2023) for a more detailed description of the task 10.5 outcomes.

3.3.1 Technical activity overview and implementation roadmap

The workplan described in D10.2 addressed mainly the FAIRness of a specific data product of the EPOS seismological community, namely **seismic waveform**. That choice was motivated by the relevance of such a primary dataset and by associated open challenges.

Four main developing activities were identified:

1) Definition of policies for PIDs.

The importance of PIDs has been discussed and it is recognised by the community, however the definition of a common policy remains challenging. We proposed a set of recommendations whereby PIDs play a central role.

A solution based on the EPIC Handle system has been successfully tested to mint PIDs for daily files containing seismic data streams. The feasibility of this approach has been demonstrated. Setting up a centrally managed PID service for the whole community would be beneficial for the uptake.

2) Population of PIDs in a community catalogue – WFCatalogue

The population of WFCatalogue, has been tested but it was decided to wait for a common agreement on the PID support before continuing with an operational rollout.

3) Implementation of a common seismology vocabulary

A seismology vocabulary⁴ has been defined and set up adopting a technical framework proposed in the EPOS ICS. Seismology was the first community pioneering that approach which was successively extended to the other EPOS community.

4) Implementation of a use case addressing seismic waveform computations on the cloud supported by the SWIRRL API.

The use case required shared access to the waveform resources by teams of users, within an exploratory virtual analysis environment. This triggered the refinement of the Generic Workspace Orchestration Framework characterising the implementation of the SWIRRL API, see Figure 1, which now allows clients to create collaborative environments combining four fundamental concepts. These are described as follows.

Session, is a Data Space where input data is stored and updated by workflows, with local versioning and provenance (SWIRRL can manage more sessions)

Workflow a common operation to stage, pre-process, update data onto the Session(s)

Service is an interactive tool (eg. Jupyter or Visual Analytics tool). A Service is attached to the Session. It has a separate Work Volume to store scientists' work (methods, outputs etc)

Service Pool is a collection of Services that share the same Session and Work Volumes.

In this framework more users can be assigned to a particular Service Pool, where they obtain personal and customisable analysis services (with dedicated computational resources), accessing shared input data, methods and results. More service pools can be connected to the same Session. In this case users in different pools won't be able to see/share each other's methods and outputs.

Once the generic framework was implemented, the realisation of the use case had to face resource limitations in the K8S cluster available at the infrastructure hosting the target waveform archive. However, the validity of the implementation triggered by the use case has been thoroughly discussed and peer reviewed, proving its usefulness and applicability in different contexts.

In addition to the activities included in the initial work plan the FAIRness of another important seismological data product was also addressed: **inventory of seismic sensors**.

A framework has been developed and deployed in operation to manage seismic inventory information. Changes of metadata descriptions are made available to the users in the form of a ChangeLog. Future plans include extending the functionalities of such a framework in order to enable full provenance support by integrating the SWIRRL API.

⁴ Epos-vocabulary-registry Vocabulary Linked Data <https://registry.epos-eu.org/ncl/> (accessed on 12th of June)

Figure 1. Workspace Orchestration Framework, for Session, Workflow, Service and ServicePool in SWIRRL API. The depicted workflow follows a hierarchical order, originating from the user and progressing through the service pool to the session. Within the session, diverse assets of varying types and origins are aggregated, thereby enabling their accessibility within the service pools. While each user within a service pool operates within their respective isolated "bubble," connected to the session, they gain access to shared resources without visibility or interaction with the outcomes of other "bubbles."

3.4 Task 10.6 - Implementation of FAIR roadmap in satellite Earth Observation community

Task 10.6 is focused on the application of the FAIR principles to satellite Earth Observation products. In particular, the task has the goal to develop awareness and share knowledge about FAIRness in the satellite Earth Observation domain to foster the application of the FAIR principles into existing practices and methods.

On the basis of the gap analysis carried out in the first 18 months of the project, some issues on the FAIRness in the satellite Earth Observation domain have been found and a list of activities, together with an implementation roadmap, has been drawn up to solve them. Readers are referred to D10.5 for a more detailed description of the task 10.6 outcomes.

Table 1: list of identified gaps, with their description, against the FAIR principle they address.

Gaps	Description	Impact on
PID	No PID system is used and applied	F1, F3 A1
Data and Metadata Life	No policy has been agreed on the lifecycle of data and metadata. Metadata preservation is not guaranteed.	A2
Vocabulary	A preliminary vocabulary has been drafted but the activity is not complete	I2

3.4.1 Technical activity overview and implementation roadmap

The envisaged activities were not subject to a selection process as this task managed in accomplishing them all. However, it required a prioritization as follows:

Data and Metadata Life: this is a short- to medium-term activity; metadata preservation has no strong impact on sustainability and is technically manageable. It needs an agreement at RIs level to be implemented in the Data Management Plan.

Vocabulary: this is a dynamic action. The building and updating of the vocabulary is an ongoing activity. Once the vocabulary is consolidated, it will be documented and resolvable using globally unique and persistent identifiers.

PID system: this is a long-term activity since it does not have a trivial solution. The adoption of a PID system has a strong impact on the financial and technical sustainability of the RIs. Indeed, a large number of satellite DDSS are live products, because they are regularly updated each time a new satellite image is available (in some cases several acquisitions per week could be available). The preservation of all generated products (instead of having a single product regularly updated) could become an unmanageable problem because each product is quite large (up to several gigabytes) and the disk space would exponentially increase. Moreover, even if several PID systems are available (e.g., DOI and handle) the services related to PID management have a cost that has to be supported by the RIs. Accordingly, a PID system technically suitable for the satellite community has to be found by investigating also its impact on financial sustainability.

The prioritization of the activities in this task was therefore crucial in ensuring all were successfully accomplished. The approach taken acknowledges the varying temporal, technical, and financial implications of each activity. The task's success underlines the importance of strategic planning, from understanding the operational issues of RIs to aligning with FAIR principles and balancing sustainability concerns. As we move forward, it is critical to maintain this perspective to continue enhancing the FAIRness and effectiveness of data management in the ENVRI community.

3.5 Task 10.7 - Marine (EMSO)

Task 10.7 was centred on enhancing the compatibility of geophysical data and metadata between EMSO and EPOS. The integration of uniform standards for both data and metadata will empower researchers to collaboratively utilise terrestrial and marine data.

This undertaking aimed to bolster the quality of metadata, data, and sensors for Ocean Bottom Seismometers (encompassing velocity-meters and accelerometers), Hydrophones, and Magnetometers (collectively referred to as OBS/H/M). These portable units are employed to establish networks in marine areas inaccessible by terrestrial networks, or to broaden terrestrial networks into oceanic regions.

Augmenting metadata bolsters the quality of data documentation and facilitates its reuse. A collaborative workflow - encompassing data curation and long-term preservation, not universally employed across EPOS and EMSO, was scrutinised for OBS/H/M data. This will ensure data is easily discoverable and accessible over an extended period. The outcome of this task is anticipated to enhance the spectrum of data products and promote the embracement of FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) principles throughout the data pipeline.

3.5.1 Technical activity overview and implementation roadmap

The process of executing technical activities for the incorporation of FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) principles started with a review of existing seismic-related data sources within EMSO. During this evaluation, we pinpointed some regional facilities already disseminating seismic data via national seismic entities (for instance, RESIF), which have already been assimilated within ORFEUS-EDIA.

EMSO ERIC has also conducted a study of the prerequisites and interfaces necessary to actively engage with ORFEUS-EIDA. Based on a FAIR evaluation and gap analysis, our strategy for technical tasks and deployment encompasses:

1. the establishment of a unifying abstraction layer, consisting of common interfaces (API);
2. the provision of quality control support for seismological data and the creation of data products;
3. the augmentation of metadata and formulation of a mutual workflow with ORFEUS-EIDA to boost integration and amplify the visibility of EMSO contributions via its regional facilities; and
4. the design of an adequate FAIRness evaluation procedure.

Specific implementation actions include:

1. the provision of EMSO data to EPOS-compatible data centres, with an initial delivery of EMSO-Azores seismology data to the EPOS-France (RESIF) data centre⁵ ;
2. the creation of and instruction in a system for generating metadata for mobile marine seismology data; and
3. the design of a processing and quality-validation node for mobile marine seismology data.

However, not all seismic data generated by EMSO nodes are amalgamated via national organisations. Therefore, dependence on national contact points to incorporate all seismic data into ORFEUS-EIDA isn't always feasible. Additionally, some regional facilities might face challenges when attempting to integrate this data into regional networks, or in some cases, the country may lack a national reference institution. Consequently, we have updated our strategy toward harmonisation and integration activities, opting for a more flexible approach that mitigates risks and possible impediments related to relying on a singular data pipeline (for instance, updating metadata at existing national contact points).

⁵ <https://seismology.resif.fr/networks/#/4G> (accessed on 12 of June 2023)

4 Conclusion

The purpose of this deliverable was to provide an overview of the prioritized list of activities defined in the previous deliverable (D10.2) and explain why they were selected and prioritized. As the key players of EPOS were involved in defining the Force11 FAIR Principles and have been actively involved in FAIR discussions through various projects and the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Working Group, FAIR has been designed into EPOS from the beginning.

Overall, EPOS can be considered at a good level in its journey to FAIR principles compliance, as the major principles have been covered through the activities that were prioritized as explained in the current deliverable and executed as described in D10.5. The various EPOS ICS-D implementations exhibit a similar level of FAIRness, realised through the progressive inclusion of these services in the EPOS ICS-C catalogue with rich metadata.

Such activities should be of course continued relying on the sustainability of the EPOS initiative. EPOS, as a mature operational RI is indeed continuously evolving to better achieve its objectives, which includes an increased compliancy with FAIR principles.

While EMSO provides services that are partially FAIR through EMSO regional agencies (i.e., not for all EMSO ERIC Regional Facilities), integrating EMSO digital assets with EPOS would greatly benefit from a harmonisation layer that includes the provision of rich metadata. This leaves the path open for future intra-RI collaborations that will take place in other contexts.

5 References

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6 Annex A - Glossary

AAAI	Authentication, Authorisation, and Accounting Infrastructure
CERIF	Common European Research Information Format
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
EPOS-DCAT-AP	DCAT Application Profile for EPOS
DDSS	Data, Data products, Software and Services
DIAS	Data and Information Access Services
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPOS Strategic Plan	Defines the activities of EPOS-ERIC
GEP	Geohazards Exploitation Platform
ICS-C	Integrated Core Services - Central Hub
ICS-D	Distributed Integrated Core Services Distributed
PID	Persistent Identifier
SDLC	Software Development Life Cycle
TCS	Thematic Core Services